

"LOST IN TRANSLATION: THE INFLUENCE OF CULTURE ON FILM TRANSLATION"

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Fazilova Nurxon

Master's degree student in Uzbekistan World Languages University

Abstract.

The film industry is an ever-growing global market, with movies being watched and appreciated across the world. However, with diverse cultures and languages, translating films for international audiences can be a challenging task. Culture plays a significant role in the translation process, and understanding the influence of culture on film translation is essential. This article aims to explore the impact of culture on film translation and how cultural considerations affect the final product.

Key words.

Humor, satire, idioms, cultural sensitivity and awareness,

Cultural Differences in Film Translation.

Films reflect the values, beliefs, and social norms of the culture in which they are created. These cultural differences can create challenges when translating films for international audiences. For instance, humor and satire in films are often culturally specific and do not always translate well into other languages. Translators must ensure that these elements are preserved and conveyed to the target audience effectively.

Similarly, cultural references, idioms, and expressions used in films can be challenging to translate. The use of language in films can convey cultural values and social norms, which can be lost in translation. For example, the film "Pulp Fiction" uses extensive profanity, which is culturally acceptable in American society but may not be suitable for all cultures. Translators must consider these cultural differences and adjust the language to make it more acceptable for the target audience.

The cultural implications of a film's title are significant, as different cultures have varying perceptions and connotations of certain words and phrases. For example, the American film "The Shawshank Redemption" was translated into French as "Les Évadés," which translates to "The Escaped." This title change was necessary as the French language does not have an equivalent word for

"Shawshank," and the concept of redemption is not as prominent in French culture. Thus, the French title better reflects the story's central theme of escape.

Another example is the film "The Hangover," which was translated into Chinese as "Do Not Think About Tomorrow." This title change reflects the Chinese cultural emphasis on moderation and responsible behavior, as the original title did not resonate with Chinese audiences who may have viewed excessive drinking as problematic behavior.

Challenges in Film Translation:

The translation of films requires not only linguistic expertise but also cultural understanding. Translators must ensure that the translation accurately conveys the original meaning and stays true to the film's cultural context. The challenge is to preserve the cultural nuances and maintain the film's artistic integrity while ensuring that it resonates with the target audience.

Additionally, some languages have different sentence structures, word order, and expressions that can make translations challenging. Translators must be aware of these differences and ensure that the translation is grammatically correct and flows naturally.

The Importance of Cultural Considerations in Film Translation:

Cultural considerations are essential in film translation to ensure that the film's message and artistic value are conveyed to the target audience accurately. A poorly translated film can affect the audience's perception of the film and impact its commercial success. Cultural sensitivity and awareness are crucial for translators to create a translation that accurately represents the film's cultural context.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, cultural differences play a significant role in film translation, and understanding the impact of culture is crucial for successful film translation. Translators must navigate cultural nuances and linguistic differences to create a translation that resonates with the target audience while preserving the film's original message and artistic value. By considering cultural factors, translators can create a high-quality film translation that enhances the film's appeal and contributes to its success in the global market.

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